

Polarized intensity (mJy beam⁻¹)

0.3

0.4

0.5

20 $z_{\text{Sp}}=1.6981$

55°36'30"

00"

35'30"

100 kpc

16^h19^m24^s 21^s

18^s

15^s

RA (J2000)

Dec (J2000)

